

CFRP RECYCLING USING DEPOLYMERIZATION OF ACID ANHYDRIDE CURED EPOXY RESIN

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1 Introduction

CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics) is widely used in sporting goods such as golf club, tennis racket and fishing rod, and recently in aircraft and automobile industry, because of its high tensile strength and lightweight property. Consequently, recycling technology is increasingly required.

We have studied the recycling technology of GFRP (Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics) of unsaturated polyester resin (UP) as a matrix resin^{1,3)}. In the study, we have found that UP easily dissolves into benzyl alcohol (BZA) with potassium triphosphate (K_3PO_4) as a catalyst at 190 °C under ordinary pressure by the mechanism of depolymerization of UP by transesterification reaction²⁾.

In this paper, we applied the method for GFRP to CFRP recycling. Acid anhydride (Ah) cured EP (EP/Ah) usually used as the matrix resin of CFRP has ester bond by the reaction between epoxy group and anhydride. So, we investigated the depolymerization of EP/Ah under ordinary pressure and found that

EP/Ah easily dissolves into BZA in standard conditions, finally recovering the carbon fiber (CF)⁴⁾.

Chemical recycling methods of thermosets were pyrolysis and solvolysis (Table 1). They were often practiced with supercritical fluids. Pyrolysis damaged fiber and filler because of high temperature. Supercritical fluid methods required high-pressure vessels that were usually expensive. Solvolyses were carried out under mild conditions, but they needed long treating time without appropriate catalysts and solvents, or required crushers and grinders. We thought that the most important factor of the practical recycling technology is the cost efficiency, and searched for a simple process. Food additives, K_3PO_4 and BZA were chosen as the reagents of the treating solution.

2 Experimental Part

2.1 Materials

The model epoxy was a commercial phenyl glycidyl ether (PGE). The acid anhydrides (Ahs)

Table 1 Comparison of chemical recycling methods of

Method	Pyrolysis		Supercritical Fluid	Solvolysis		
	Gas phase	Vegetable oil		Liquid phase	Glycolysis	Our method
Temperature	250-900 °C	350 °C	180-400 °C	200-440 °C	150-250 °C	<200 °C
Pressure	closed,ordinary	ordinary	2-22 MPa	ordinary-2 MPa	ordinary-20 MPa	ordinary
Solvent	no	vegetable oil	water,alcohol,phenol	hydrogen donor solvent	glycol	alcohol
Catalyst	no	no	no	salt	acid or alkali	salt
Grinding size	< 10 mm	< 5 mm	< 1 mm	< 5 mm	< 1 mm	-
Recyclate	gas,oil	oil	monomer	monomer,oil	Oligomer	Oligomer

were succinic anhydride (ScAh), cis-1,2-cyclohexanedicarboxylic anhydride (ChAh), cis-4-cyclohexene-1,2-dicarboxylic anhydride (CheAh) purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd.

The hardening accelerator was 2,4,6-tris(dimethylaminomethyl) phenol purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd. K_3PO_4 and BZA were commercially available from Taiyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd and Sun Chemical Co., Ltd, respectively.

2.2 Synthesis of a model matrix

The model matrix that consists of PGE and Ahs were introduced in a test tube. The reactive mixture was heated at 80 °C for 1.0 h followed by the heating at 150 °C for 1.0 h. The oil bath was used to heat the mixture.

2.3 Depolymerization of a model matrix

The model matrixes, BZA and K_3PO_4 were introduced in a test tube. The reactive mixture was heated at 180 °C for 10.0 h.

2.4 Characterization

1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured at a room temperature with a JEOL AL-400 (400 MHz) NMR spectrometer. Model compounds were dissolved in d_6 -dimethylsulfoxide (d_6 -DMSO).

In a suffix of signals, alphabet shows the degree of signal intensity (s:strong, m:middle, w:weak) and numerals show number of signals.

Spectra Database for Organic Compounds SDBS was used to assign the NMR spectrum. This is a free site organized by National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), Japan.

Scheme 1 Possible polymerization reaction of model matrix

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Polymerization reaction of model matrix

The model matrix was synthesized stoichiometrically by the reaction between PGE and Ahs with catalyst.

NMR signal attribution of PGE, ScAh, ChAh and CheAh are shown in Fig 1, and the theoretical polymerization reaction with anhydride is shown in Scheme 1.

Fig. 1 Attribution of PGE, ScAh, ChAh and CheAh in NMR (Italic : 1H NMR, Bold : ^{13}C NMR)

3.2 Characterization of the polymerization products

(1) PGE/ScAh

The NMR signal attribution of PGE/ScAh is shown in Fig 2 and NMR signals of polymerization product, PGE and ScAh are shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Fig. 2 Attribution of PGE/ScAh in NMR (alphabet : ¹H, numeral : ¹³C)

Table 2
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ¹H NMR

Attribution	¹ H NMR σ(ppm)		
	PGE/ScAh	PGE	ScAh
(a)	2.51m4		
(a)	2.58s		
		2.71s7	
		2.85s4	3.01s1
	3.39s	3.31s11	
	3.56w		
(d)	3.93w	3.83s4	
(d)	4.02w2		
	4.06w		
(b)	4.12m		
(b)	4.29m	4.29s4	
(c)	5.30m		
(e)	6.94s3	6.84s11	
(e)	7.27m	7.30s13	

Table 3
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ¹³C NMR

Attribution	¹³ C NMR σ(ppm)		
	PGE/ScAh	PGE	ScAh
1	28.54m3		28.34m3
		43.95m	
		49.96m	
	62.16m2		
4	65.91m2		
	66.77w		
3	68.95w		
5	69.68m	69.13m	
7	114.58s2	115.25s	
9	120.86m3	121.44m	
8	128.52m3		
		130.16s	
6	158.02m2	159.04m	
2	171.61m5		170.65m1

The disappearance of epoxide signals of PGE at both σ2.71 ppm and σ2.85 ppm of ¹H NMR and at both σ43.95 ppm and σ49.96 ppm of ¹³C NMR indicates the cleavage of epoxides and progress of polymerization reaction.

¹H NMR signals at σ3.39 ppm, σ3.56 ppm and σ4.06 ppm and ¹³C NMR signals at σ62.16 ppm and σ66.77 ppm may suggest the possibility of unreacted materials or polymerization reaction between PGEs.

(2) PGE/ChAh

The NMR signal attribution of PGE/ScAh is shown in Fig 3 and NMR signals of polymerization product, PGE and ChAh are shown in Tables 4 and 5.

Fig. 3 Attribution of PGE/ChAh in NMR (alphabet : ¹H, numeral : ¹³C)

Table 4
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ¹H NMR

Attribution	¹ H NMR σ(ppm)		
	PGE/ChAh	PGE	ChAh
(c)	1.32m		
			1.50s5
			1.53s4
(b)	1.67m		
(b)	1.84m		1.81m10
			1.90m21
	2.71w4	2.71s7	
(a)	2.84w4	2.85s4	
			3.14s5
			3.17s6
	3.34s6	3.31s11	
(f)	3.85w3	3.83s4	
(f)	4.05w		
(d)	4.24w	4.29s4	
(d)	4.30w4		
(e)	5.26w		
(g)	6.95m4	6.84s11	
(g)	7.30m5	7.30s13	

Table 5
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ^{13}C NMR

Attribution	^{13}C NMR σ (ppm)		
	PGE/ChAh	PGE	ChAh
3	22.88w		22.29m1
2	24.52w		24.86m1
	25.57w		
1	41.59m		40.99m1
	43.78w	43.95m	
	49.75w	49.96m	
	62.01w		
6	65.94w		
5	66.81m		
7	69.01m	69.13m	
9	114.43s2	115.25s	
11	120.86m3	121.44m	
10	128.52s2		
		130.16s	
8	158.24m3	159.04m	
4	172.28m2		172.94m3

The weakness of strength that epoxide signals of PGE at both σ 2.71 ppm and σ 2.85 ppm of ^1H NMR and at both σ 43.95 ppm and σ 49.96 ppm of ^{13}C NMR indicates the cleavage of epoxides and progress of polymerization reaction.

σ 2.71 ppm, σ 2.84 ppm and σ 3.34 ppm of ^1H NMR, σ 25.57 ppm, σ 43.78 ppm, σ 49.75 ppm and σ 62.01 ppm of ^{13}C NMR are possibility of unreacted materials or polymerization reaction between PGEs.

(3) PGE/CheAh

The NMR signal attribution of PGE/CheAh is shown in Fig 4. And NMR signals of polymerization product, PGE and CheAh are shown in Tables 6 and 7.

Scheme 2 Possible depolymerization mechanism of PGE/Ahs

Fig. 4 Attribution of PGE/CheAh in NMR (alphabet : ^1H , numeral : ^{13}C)

Table 6
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ^1H NMR

Attribution	^1H NMR σ (ppm)		
	PGE/CheAh	PGE	CheAh
(b)	2.27m6		2.29s10
(b)	2.36m7		2.34s7
	2.76w5	2.71s7	
		2.85s4	
	3.02m10		
(a)	3.36s5	3.31s11	3.41s12
(f)	3.89w	3.83s4	
(f)	4.03m7		
(d)	4.22w	4.29s4	
(d)	4.30w		
(e)	5.24w		
(c)	5.56m		5.98s13
(g)	6.88m	6.84s11	
(g)	7.24m	7.30s13	

Table 7
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ^{13}C NMR

Attribution	^{13}C NMR σ (ppm)		
	PGE/CheAh	PGE	CheAh
2	25.24m3		24.49m3
1	26.50w1		40.09m1
		43.95m	
		49.96m	
	62.12m2		
6	65.86m3		
5	66.50w1		
7	69.50m3	69.13m	
9	114.46s2	115.25s	
11	121.01m3	121.44m	
3	124.86m2		
10	128.45s		128.31m6
		130.16s	
8	157.97m3	159.04m	
4	171.97m2		174.26m2

The disappearance of epoxides signals from PGE at both σ 2.71 ppm and σ 2.85 ppm of ^1H NMR and at both σ 43.95 ppm and σ 49.96 ppm of ^{13}C NMR indicated the cleavage of epoxides and progress of polymerization reaction.

σ 2.76 ppm and σ 3.02 ppm of ^1H NMR signals, σ 62.21 ppm of ^{13}C NMR signals may suggest the possibility of unreacted materials or polymerization reaction between PGEs.

3.3 Proposed depolymerization mechanism

In Scheme 2, we showed the proposed mechanism of the depolymerization of thermosets under ordinary pressure by the BZA. As shown, the most probable mechanism is thought to be the transesterification.

Following the proposed mechanism shown in Scheme 2, the depolymerization products with BZA may be dibenzyl ester derivative from the anhydride and 3-phenoxy-1, 2-propanediol from PGE.

3.4 Characterization of the depolymerization products

(1) Depolymerization of PGE/ScAh (DEP(PGE/ScAh))

The NMR signals of DEP(PGE/ScAh), PhPD and DbSuc are shown in Tables 8 and 9. NMR signal attribution of DEP(PGE/ScAh) is shown in Fig 5. Spectra always contain signals of BZA as a solvent.

Table 8
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ^1H NMR

Attribution	^1H NMR σ (ppm)			
	DEP(PGE/ScAh)	PhPD	DbSuc	BZA
				2.24m11
	2.50w5			
(l)	2.63s3		2.69	
(i)	3.39w1	3.49		
(h)	3.47w2	3.69		
(d)	3.85w6	3.78		
(f)	3.94w2	3.83		
(g)	4.01w4	3.96		
(e)	4.12w1	4.07		
	4.51s1			4.62s13
(k)	5.09s1		5.11	
	5.19w1			
(c)		6.87		
(a)	6.93m12	6.94		
(b)	7.23w9	7.24		7.22m7
(j)	7.32s20		7.32	7.32s6

Table 9
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ^{13}C NMR

Attribution	^{13}C NMR σ (ppm)			
	DEP(PGE/ScAh)	PhPD	DbSuc	BZA
14	28.66m1		29.13	
7	62.92s2	63.73		
	65.42m2			65.14s2
12	66.77w1		66.46	
5	69.45w2	69.05		
6	69.99w1	70.62		
3	114.43m3	114.62		
1	120.39m2	121.28		
	126.61s3			126.92s1
8	127.78m2			127.54s1
9	128.03w2		128.19	
10	128.24w2		128.52	128.46s1
2	129.44m2	129.55		
11	136.06m1		135.81	
	142.53m1			140.81s1
4	158.77w2	158.47		
13	171.88w2		171.94	

As a result of NMR analysis, the signals of DEP(PGE/ScAh) consisted with those of PhPD and DbSuc. So we thought that DEP(PGE/ScAh) consists of PhPD and DbSuc. On the other hand, signals of σ 2.50 ppm and σ 5.19 ppm were not attributed to PhPD and DbSuc, suggesting the existence of the side reaction products.

(2)Depolymerization of PGE/ChAh(DEP(PGE/ChAh))

The NMR signals of DEP(PGE/ChAh) are shown in Tables 10 and 11. NMR signal attribution of DEP(PGE/ChAh) is shown in Fig 6.

Table 10
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ¹H NMR

Attribution	¹ H NMR σ (ppm)			
	DEP(PGE/ChAh)	PhPD	DbHp	BZA
(p)	1.26w1			
(o)	1.34w1		1.50	
(n)	1.66w1		1.53	
(m)	1.85w1		1.81	
(d)			1.90	
	2.49m5			2.24m11
(h)	2.51w1			
(l)	2.80w1		2.69	
(i)	3.43w1	3.49		
	3.50w2	3.78		
(f)	3.80w1	3.83		
(g),(h)	3.90w1	3.96		
(e)	4.07w3	4.07		
	4.52s1			4.62s13
	5.02w2			
(k)	5.21m1		5.11	
		6.87		
(a),(c)	6.92m5	6.94		
(b)	7.23m9	7.24		7.22m7
(j)	7.31s14		7.32	7.32s6

Table 11
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ¹³C NMR

Attribution	¹³ C NMR σ (ppm)			
	DEP(PGE/ChAh)	PhPD	DbHp	BZA
16	23.15w1		23.23	
15	24.61w1		23.7	
14	28.48w1		29.13	
7	62.86s2	63.73		
	65.45w1			65.14s2
	66.01w1			
12	66.35w1		66.46	
5	69.48w1	69.05		
6	70.04w1	70.62		
3	114.45m1	114.62		
1	120.64w3	121.28		
	126.63s3			126.92s1
10	127.80m2		128.19	127.54s1
8,9	128.40m1		128.52	128.46s1
2	129.48m1	129.55		
11	136.11m2		135.81	
	142.56s1			140.81s1
4	158.52w3	158.47		
13	174.01w1	172.94	171.94	

As a result of NMR analysis, the signals of DEP(PGE/ChAh) consisted with those of PhPD and DbHp. So we thought that DEP(PGE/ChAh) consists of PhPD and DbHp. On the other hand, signals of σ 5.02ppm of ¹H NMR, σ 66.01 ppm of ¹³C NMR were not attributed to PhPD and DbHp, suggesting the existence of the side reaction products.

(3)Depolymerization of PGE/CheAh (DEP(PGE/CheAh))

The NMR signals of DEP(PGE/CheAh), PhPD and DbTp are shown in Tables 12 and 13. NMR signal attribution of DEP(PGE/CheAh) is shown in Fig 7.

Table 12
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ¹H NMR

Attribution	¹ H NMR σ (ppm)			
	DEP(PGE/CheAh)	PhPD	DbTp	BZA
(n)	2.29w1		2.29	2.24m11
(m)	2.38w1		2.34	
	2.49w3		2.6	
(l)	2.70w1		2.63	
	3.03w1			
(d)	3.40w1		3.41	
(i)	3.47w2	3.49		
		3.78		
(f)	3.80w1	3.83		
(g)(h)	3.92w1	3.96		
(e)	4.07w2	4.07		
	4.51s1			4.62s13
	5.05w3			
(k)	5.20m1		5.11	
(o)	5.61w3		5.98	
		6.87		
(a)(c)	6.91m2	6.94		
(b)	7.23m12	7.24		7.22m7
(j)	7.31s9		7.32	7.32s6

Table 13
Signal attribution and chemical shifts in ^{13}C NMR

Attribution	^{13}C NMR σ (ppm)			
	DEP(PGE/CheAh)	PhPD	DbTp	BZA
14	25.43w1		23.16	
15	27.0w1		24.49	
7	62.93s2	63.73		
	65.68w3			65.14s2
12	66.79w1			
5	69.46w1	69.05		
6	70.00w1	70.62		
3	114.48w1	114.62		
1	120.62w3	121.28		
	124.85w1			
	126.61s3			126.92s1
9	127.76m2		128.19	127.54s1
2,10	128.36m4		128.52	128.46s1
		129.55		
11,16	136.0w1		135.81	
	142.53m1			140.81s1
4	158.01w2	158.47		
13	172.01w1	172.94	171.94	

As a result of NMR analysis, the signals of DEP(PGE/CheAh) consisted with those of PhPD and DbTp. So we thought that DEP(PGE/CheAh) consists of PhPD and DbTp. On the other hand, signals of $\sigma 3.03$ ppm and $\sigma 5.05$ ppm of ^1H NMR, $\sigma 124.85$ ppm of ^{13}C NMR were not attributed to PhPD and DbTp, suggesting the existence of the side reaction products.

Fig. 5 Attribution of depolymerization products in NMR

Fig. 6 Attribution of depolymerization products in NMR

Fig. 7 Attribution of depolymerization products in NMR

4. Conclusions

In this work the chemical recycling of the epoxy resin cured with anhydrides were investigated. Synthesis of a model compound enables to study the polymerization and depolymerization reaction.

The polymerization and depolymerization products were identified by NMR analysis.

From the NMR analyses of depolymerization of PGE/Ahs model compounds, we found that benzyester and bisdiol are formed by the depolymerization of the thermoset under ordinary pressure. The depolymerization mechanism of PGE/Ahs was the transesterification with BZA, so we concluded that the depolymerization were mainly transesterification reaction accelerated with K_3PO_4 .

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